

D-Exit: A Decentralised Early Exit of Inference Framework for Swarm Systems

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Abstract. The increasing complexity and intensity of computational tasks related to Machine Learning necessitates flexible solutions that can be implemented across the IoT-edge-cloud continuum, relying on heterogeneous distributed deployments like swarm systems. These solutions are required to offer secure and reliable deployments, addressing key challenges such as the communication and computational resource scarcity and the near real-time needs of modern applications. This paper presents a decentralised early-exit of inference framework for swarm systems (D-Exit) based on a peer-to-peer communication, distributing the inference process across swarm nodes, reducing the computational burden of individual participants and minimizing the single point of failure risk. Numerical evaluations based on simulated swarms demonstrate the key metrics involved in the D-Exit framework, including the computational load of the nodes and the trade-off between the inference latency and the model accuracy.

Keywords: Early-exit of inference · energy efficiency · swarm systems · decentralized inference · peer-to-peer communication · DNN models · computational efficiency

1 Introduction

1.1 Data-Intensive Applications and Lightweight Methods

Cross-domain, ML-assisted applications utilize the concept of the IoT-edge-cloud continuum, encompassing the resources that are located at multiple hierarchical levels of the computational architecture [20, 16]. These applications exhibit increasingly challenging requirements, especially related to the computational and network complexities, along with the need for reduced energy consumption

towards the development of greener solutions [1, 25]. To address these requirements, several lightweight methods have been proposed in the literature, targeting to jointly minimize the energy consumption of the involved computational resources and the energy required for data transfer between the processing nodes, while also maintaining an acceptable application latency [18, 9]. Apart from the hierarchical architecture of the IoT-edge-cloud continuum, modern applications are also developed to rely on heterogeneous distributed systems, i.e., multiple devices that exhibit diverse hardware resources, networking specifications, operating systems, and distributed protocols. To this end heterogeneous, intelligent, dynamic, and fully decentralised swarm systems have been developed to solve application tasks, requiring highly complex management processes [19, 3].

The edge or far edge computational-intensive tasks are increasingly related to Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML), since AI/ML models are intended to be integrated in a native-AI architecture, spanning across infrastructure, network and application domains [21, 24]. Meanwhile, data privacy concerns and time-delay problems constitute key challenges for cloud computing, and ML models are pushed towards the edge and end devices, closer to the origin of the data. To this end, lightweight methods and communication protocols for enabling the training of these models at the edge have emerged (e.g., federated/swarm learning), aiming at reducing the network overhead and the energy consumption associated with the data transfer [10, 5]. In addition, lightweight techniques for the inference process of the ML models have been also developed, providing considerable gains especially for Deep Neural Networks (DNNs). DNNs that are located at the network edge are designed to work continuously, providing their results to the end user. Inference of the model with new samples is therefore becoming a constant process, exhibiting a significant energy footprint. Lightweight techniques typically balance the trade-off between inference time, computational complexity, energy consumption and the accuracy of the model outputs [9].

Several lightweight techniques for ML inference have been studied in the literature, such as the pruning of the DNNs, i.e., removing the least significant weights of the model and the quantization approach, that uses lower precision in the weights and activation functions to simplify the DNN [4, 11]. Furthermore, the recent knowledge distillation method replaces the original DNN (teacher) with a more lightweight version of the model (student) that can be utilized for the continuous inference process [17, 13]. Finally, the early-exit of inference is a valuable technique for enhancing the energy-efficiency that involves the partial feed-forward process during the inference, stopping the processing of the input once the prediction confidence is adequate, hence preserving computational resources and inference latency [22].

In specific, the latter early-exit of inference method entails the insertion of additional exit layers (named branches) between the intermediate hidden layers of the DNN during its training phase. The additional exits of the DNN are trained similar to typical supervised learning. Towards this direction, the loss is computed in the exits using the data labels, whereas during the backpropagation,

the exits closer to the input layer assist in solving the vanishing gradient problem [14]. Once the DNN is trained and is used for inference, the respective exit pathway is selected when the prediction confidence exceeds a specific threshold [12]. In this way, the correct classification of an inference sample leads to the early-exit of inference, i.e., the feed-forward operation stops and the activation signals are not propagated through the entire DNN, hence saving computational resources and inference latency.

1.2 Challenges and Related Work

Traditional centralised models that are based on cloud resources for inference face several challenges to the requirements of the modern applications. First, the network latency for sending data to a central location and receiving results (e.g., model inference outputs) can be prohibitive for real-time applications. Secondly, network constraints may impose additional delays or congestion, since large amounts of data are typically generated by the edge devices and are transferred vertically to the cloud. In addition, data privacy is also considered a key limitation, since sensitive data are sent over public network links and are aggregated in a central location, which may be subjected to cybersecurity attacks. Finally, the number of IoT sensors and edge devices is growing rapidly and the centralised cloud computing approach struggles to keep pace with the increasingly demanding data transfer requests, raising scalability issues.

On the other hand, the majority of end devices (IoT sensors, mobile phones, etc.) are unable to host a whole DNN model locally due to resource (memory, CPU, battery) constraints and strict latency requirements. Offloading to more powerful computational resources (for instance, a cluster of edge servers or cloud resources) is typically used, inherently involving increased vertical network traffic towards higher hierarchical layers, as well as increased delay due to network congestion, regardless of the latency performance of the model.

To address these problems, several research works can be found in the literature regarding the distributed early-exit technique. The authors in [15] propose a distributed DNN architecture in the hierarchical computing continuum, i.e., cloud, edge and end devices, illustrating the benefits of fault tolerance and data privacy during the inference process. They jointly train the additional model branches, minimizing the use of computational and communication resources and illustrating the trade-off between the local data processing on the end devices and the accuracy of the model outputs. Moreover, the authors in [26] propose a two-branch model architecture named *Big.Little*, suitable for artificial intelligence IoT (AIoT) applications. In this architecture, the little model branches are deployed directly in the AIoT devices that have limited computing and memory resources, while the big branch is deployed on the cloud, using abundant computational resources for increasing the prediction accuracy. The scheme uses federated learning (FL) for training the different model parts. Similarly, the authors in [27] introduce a hierarchical distributed architecture and use FL for training the two separate model parts that are deployed on multiple

end devices and edge servers respectively. To reduce the exploitation of the computing resources, they introduce an early-exit in the primary model part hosted in the end devices and they perform dynamical model updates in the already deployed model branches.

In addition, the authors in [2] introduce a model-distributed inference (MDI) architectural approach, illustrating how the design and development of MDI coupled with the early-exit technique (associated with offloading policies and data admission at the source) can lead to increased utilization of the edge computational resources, while maintaining acceptable levels of model accuracy. Concerning the offloading policies, the authors in [8] replace the passive offloading decision-making based on the prediction confidence with a low-cost prediction engine that provides forecasts on where the network will exit, reducing the network overhead to the remaining DNN layers. The proposed approach also optimally configures the required computational resources towards energy efficiency, while retaining the inference accuracy and latency compared to state-of-the-art exiting strategies. Finally, the authors in [23] deal with the adaptation of the early-exit method to regression tasks by introducing an additional output named Learn to Exit. Notably, one of the key advantages of all the aforementioned early-exit methods is the inherent data privacy. The devices that have a specific branch do not forward to the nodes that host the successive model part locally-stored data, but rather the output of an intermediate layer, which appear nonsensical to a human and are practically considered encoded.

The aforementioned approaches that are based on the early-exit technique are effectively adapted to the modern hierarchical architectures, spreading the DNN model across the computing continuum. However, these approaches need to be modified and integrated in larger distributed systems, where the environment is extremely dynamic (the status of a distributed node changes rapidly depending on varying network conditions) and the participating distributed nodes are heterogeneous in terms of hardware and software resources. To this end, highly distributed systems (e.g., swarms) require complex management and offloading strategies for integrating the early-exit of DNNs, targeting to disseminate the computational burden of model inference among several swarm nodes.

1.3 Paper Outline and Contributions

This paper presents a decentralised early-exit of inference framework for swarm systems (D-Exit), utilizing a combination of distributed computing, early-exit strategies, and peer-to-peer networking between the node participants. The key contributions of this work include:

- The presented framework implements early-exit offloading strategies that allow for adaptive computation based on the complexity of the input. In this context, uncomplicated inferences are completed at the swarm nodes that host the primary model part, reducing the latency and overall computational load, while effectively utilizing the available network resources.

- D-Exit distributes the model inference process across multiple swarm nodes, reducing the computational burden on any single point in the system and minimizing the single point of failure risk. The swarm nodes assume the roles of IoT/edge/cloud nodes of the typical hierarchical computing architecture, depending on the model branch that they host and can be used interchangeably to feed-forward an inference sample.
- The communication between the swarm members is conducted in a fully distributed peer-to-peer manner, providing zero dependencies on centralized nodes, while supporting dynamic adaptation to varying network conditions. This is especially critical in wireless environments, where the stability of the network impacts the node availability.
- The D-Exit framework enhances the resilience of the distributed early-exit, since it allows for seamless addition or removal of nodes, enabling the application to scale dynamically with respect to the swarm size.
- The simulation results validate the performance of the D-Exit framework, considering both the training of the early-exit models in terms of accuracy performance, but also their deployment in a simulated swarm system of 14 nodes, measuring key metrics such as the decentralized inference time and the computational load sharing among the peers. Finally, we provide the open-source code of D-Exit on Github¹ to allow researchers to experiment and advance the framework.

2 Architecture Model Overview

The high-level architecture of the D-Exit is depicted in Fig. 1, where the key software components constituting the framework and their interconnections are outlined. In specific, the functional role of these components is described below:

1. **IoT/End Device:** The IoT/End Device is typically a resource-constrained node that serves as the entry point for inference requests. These requests are initiated by an end-user (in case of a smartphone) or by the functional operation of the device (e.g., IoT sensor, camera, etc.). The key features of the IoT/End Device include the initial processing of the inference request and the feed-forward operation up to the first exit, deciding whether to forward the request to higher layer nodes based on the prediction confidence.
2. **Edge Node:** The role of the Edge Node is to receive the inference requests conveyed by the IoT/End Device, acting as an intermediate processing unit with more computational power. To this end, the Edge Node typically hosts a part of the model that requires increased computational complexity, implementing its own early-exit strategy. Similar to the lower-level IoT/End Device nodes, the Edge node forwards the most challenging cases to the Cloud Node, based on the prediction confidence at its early-exit.
3. **Cloud Node:** The Cloud Node represents the final hierarchical layer of the D-Exit framework, exhibiting increased computational capacity in terms of

¹ <https://github.com/anaskalt/dexit>

Fig. 1. High-level architecture of the D-Exit framework architecture and its building blocks.

resources. The hidden layers and the final exit of the neural network that are included in the Cloud Node typically require considerable computational resources. Moreover, the Cloud Node handles the most challenging inference scenarios, since it provides high-accuracy results of input samples that have not exited in previous layers.

4. **Network layer:** The P2P Network Layer forms the communication backbone of the D-Exit framework, since it includes peer discovery mechanisms during the initialization phase, while it utilizes efficient routing protocols for the inter-node communication of the inference intermediate requests, following the hierarchical model architecture. In addition, the network layer supports various transport protocols, along with Network Address Translation (NAT) traversal capabilities to ensure smooth transmission in resource-constrained environments like swarm systems.
5. **Network State Management:** The Network State Management component acts as a memory of the swarm system, tracking the statuses of the peers that participate in the D-Exit framework, having an overview of the overall swarm topology. Furthermore, this component tracks the online inference requests that and their statuses, as well as the workload distribution across the swarm nodes.

It is worth noting that multiple nodes in a large swarm system can assume one of the functional roles, i.e., multiple nodes can act as IoT/End Device hosting the first part of the DNN model.

3 Implementation Considerations

3.1 D-Exit Workflow

During the initialization phase of the D-Exit, the Network Layer implements a peer discovery mechanism and establishes the connection between the swarm

Fig. 2. Step-by-step workflow for the D-Exit initialization and operation upon the reception of an inference request.

nodes. The swarm topology is also acknowledged to the Network State Management, acting as a collective memory of the system. The P2P layer utilizes `libp2p` to ensure secure communication between the nodes, featuring an asynchronous pub-sub process for efficient broadcast of the network states to achieve synchronization, as well as a message chunking functionality of the feed-forward data during the inference process to comply with potential bandwidth constraints in the swarm systems. It should be noted that the each peer waits until the required number of decentralized nodes/peers (configurable by the user) join the D-Exit framework before the inference process can start. Fig. 2 workflow demonstrates how the system processes inference requests across the distributed network:

- *Step 1 (Inference Initiation)*: An inference request is initiated at the IoT/End Device. The IoT/End Device performs initial processing on the input data. This request typically originates from batter-constrained devices with mini-

- mal computational resources (e.g., cameras, sensors, etc.) or is directly created at the end user devices that host ML applications (e.g., mobile phones).
- *Step 2 (IoT/End Device Early Exit)*: If the confidence threshold is met at the IoT/End Device, the inference terminates here. The result is returned immediately, minimising latency.
 - *Step 3 (Forwarding to Edge Node)*: If the Edge Device cannot meet the confidence threshold, the intermediate result is forwarded to the Edge Node. The P2P network layer handles the efficient transfer of data.
 - *Step 4 (Edge Node Processing)*: The Edge Node receives the intermediate result and continues processing. It applies its own early-exit strategy based on confidence thresholds.
 - *Step 5 (Edge Early Exit or Forward)*: If the Edge node meets the confidence threshold, it terminates the inference and returns the result. If further processing is needed, the intermediate result is forwarded to the Cloud Node.
 - *Step 6 (Cloud Node Final Processing)*: The Cloud Node receives the most complex cases. It performs the final inference steps and returns the result.
 - *Step 7 (Result Propagation)*: The final inference result is propagated back through the network to the originating IoT/End Device. The Network State is updated with the completed inference result.

3.2 Swarm Implementation

Following the D-Exit workflow, the deployment of the different parts of the model according to the early-exit splitting can be conducted directly at the swarm nodes. Therefore, the same copy of a early-exit model part can be hosted in multiple swarm nodes for redundancy purposes, as well as for minimizing the inference latency and for sharing the computational burden of the processing. To this end, the energy capacity and resources of specific swarm members (e.g., battery-powered) are not individually reduced, enabling the energy efficiency and the resilience of the swarm system. The considered architecture is shown in Fig. 3 following a layered hierarchical scheme. In this context, I swarm nodes possess the first part of the model with N_1 hidden layers, containing the branch with the first early-exit (B_1 hidden layers and an E_1 output layer), exhibiting the functional capabilities of an IoT/End device. On the other hand, E swarm nodes host the second part of the model (denoted edge nodes) with N_2 hidden layers that also includes the branch with the second early-exit (B_2 hidden layers and an E_2 output layer). Finally, C swarm nodes host the last branch of the model that contains B_3 hidden layers and the E_3 output layer, leading to the final exit 3 (denoted cloud nodes).

It is worth mentioning that the notation IoT/End device, Edge and Cloud here may also reflect the hierarchical architectural layers of a continuum, indicating that the higher layers exhibit increased computational capability than the lower-level swarm nodes. The swarm system may be heterogeneous in terms of computational resources and the nodes with increased capacity assume the functional role of cloud nodes. On the other hand, nodes with limited capabilities and strict energy constrains can host the first part of the model, assuming the

Fig. 3. Architectural view of the swarm nodes hosting the different parts of the early-exit model parts.

role of IoT/End device. For purposes of balancing the computational load within the swarm system, we use $C < E < I$, indicating that the majority of the swarm nodes host the first part of the model, while few peers assume the role of the Cloud nodes. As aforementioned, the communication between the swarm peers is peer-to-peer based on the `libp2p` following the hierarchical architecture, i.e., the nodes of each layer can be linked only to the next-tier nodes and communication between same-layer peers is not feasible.

4 Numerical Results

In this section, we numerically evaluate the proposed D-Exit framework, quantifying key metrics such as testing accuracy, latency and computational resource allocation. All experimental evaluations that are presented in this section were conducted using a representative subset of the CIFAR-10 dataset, consisting of $32 \times 32 \times 3$ RGB images across 10 object classes [6]. Moreover, the base model architecture was the Visual Geometry Group (VGG-16) that includes 138M parameters, 13 convolutional layers and 3 fully connected layers. Noteworthy, the baseline inference performance of the original VGG model (without splitting to model parts) is a 92.5% test set accuracy, while the baseline inference latency per sample is 2.35ms.

4.1 Early-Exit Model Training

Regarding the training of the early-exit model parts before their deployment in the swarm system, three different versions of the VGG model were created, based on the splitting strategy. In specific, the VGG-16 base architecture was utilized, enhanced with 3 intermediate classifier heads (2K, 4K and 8K parameters respectively for the three model branches depicted in Fig. 3). It is worth noting that the accurate training process of the model enables the adaptive early-exit through intermediate classification points during the inference process. As an exit decision

mechanism, a confidence-based thresholding was used with $\tau = [0.9, 0.8, 0.7]$ for the exits [1, 2, 3] respectively and the multi-exit loss training with equal weighting across all exits was employed. Finally, the three model variants that were utilized in the present paper differ in the model split percentage, i.e., the Front-weighted (50/30/20%) distribution per exit (strengthening the IoT/End device model parts), the Rear-weighted (35/25/40%) distribution per exit (representing increased computation capabilities of Cloud nodes) and the Evenly-weighted (33/34/33%) distribution per exit (constituting a fair policy of sharing the computational load among the swarm peers). In addition, the training configuration parameters for all variants include the Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) optimizer, a learning rate $l_r = 0.001$ with cosine decay, a batch size of 128 and 200 training epochs.

The exit distribution analysis results are shown in Fig. 4, illustrating the sample allocation at the exit points across the three splitting strategies. Evidently, the Front-weighted and the Rear-weighted models achieve an imbalanced distribution with (50/30/20%) and (35/25/40%) samples across the three exits, while the Evenly-weighted model variant achieves a balanced distribution with 3,300 samples exiting at the IoT/Edge device layer, 3,400 samples exiting at the Edge node layer, and 3,300 samples at the final Cloud node exit, leading to even computational burden among the swarm participants.

Furthermore, the individual accuracies for the different exits and the splitting strategies are also depicted in Fig. 4. Evidently, the testing accuracy gradually increases in cases that the inference samples are propagated to hierarchically higher exits, validating the suitable training of the models. Moreover, the Front-weighted variant achieves the highest early exit accuracy (Exit 1: 81.2% vs 77.1% vs 74.8%) due to increased early computational allocation. This also leads to fastest average inference, i.e., 1.45ms vs 1.78ms vs 2.12ms per sample, resulting in 32-46% speedup with respect to the 2.35ms baseline inference latency, showcasing the trade-off of the early-exit mechanism between increased latency and decreased accuracy. Furthermore, trade-off results between the overall (across exits) model accuracy and the computational savings due to the early-exit mechanism are also derived. To this end, although the overall test accuracy is decreased compared to the original model (84.7, 85.2 and 86.3% for the three splitting strategies respectively), the computational savings significantly increase (45.5%, 35.0%, 33.3% average Floating-point Operation Per Second reduction).

4.2 D-Exit Inference Results

As aforementioned, the D-Exit framework deploys the trained early-exit model versions in the swarm nodes in a decentralized manner, following the different strategies and architecture presented in Fig. 3. In this subsection, we evaluate key metrics of the D-Exit scheme deployed in a small swarm system. In this context, we produce a topology with 8 IoT/End Devices, 4 Edge nodes and 2 Cloud nodes, hosting the corresponding early-exit model splits in a 2D space of $20 \times 20 \text{ m}^2$. It should be noted that the connection among peers is performed in a P2P manner, utilizing `libp2p`. Moreover, three different peer connection

Fig. 4. Comparison between the three splitting strategies (Front-, Evenly-, Rear-weighted) and across the three early-exits: (a) Number of inference samples terminated in each exit; (b) Accuracy of the model against the testing samples for each exit.

strategies are tested: (i) the *closest* strategy, where the peers that contain a model split send their feedforward data to their closest node that contains the higher-layer model split, in case of low confidence level; (ii) the *first-available* strategy, where the peers that do not achieve high confidence results to exit early forward the inference data to the higher-layer node that is available, i.e., currently not executing additional operations and ready to process the receiving inference input; (iii) the *random* strategy, where the peers choose randomly the next-layer node in case of low confidence results. The D-Exit framework runs on a normal PC with the following characteristics: CPU i7-8700, 3.2 GHz, RAM 8 GB with no GPU usage, whereas the swarm nodes are deployed as processes in separate virtual machines (VMs).

Indicative results using the front-weighted splitting strategy can be shown in Fig. 5. In specific, the inference time in each exit of the neural network is depicted across the considered connection strategies in a realistic swarm system. Notably, the inference time in each node includes the processing time of the feedforward data (which is not prioritized and runs in parallel with other node computational tasks), as well as the average communication overhead between the different layers/splits of the ML model. The latter latency component is measured in the current deployment at approximately 20 ms from the first to the second model split (Edge Nodes) and 45 ms from the Edge Node to the final model split (Cloud Nodes) on average.

Moreover, Fig. 5 quantifies the CPU usage distribution for the different exits/layers across the participating swarm nodes. Evidently, the total inference time increases when higher-layer model splits are included in the inference process, as expected. In addition, the *first-available* communication strategy between the swarm nodes outperforms the other two schemes in terms of CPU usage of the participating swarm nodes, as well as decreasing the inference time due to the delay minimization of the feedforward packet processing in the receiving node. Noteworthy, in all strategies the swarm nodes share the computational

Fig. 5. Comparison between the three communication strategies in the swarm system (*Closest*, *First*, *Random*) and across the three early-exits: (a) Inference latency measured at each exit; (b) CPU usage of each node.

burden of model inference compared to a full DNN model that is hosted in a single node.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

The presented D-Exit scheme offers a distributed inference solution suitable for swarm systems and the IoT-edge-cloud continuum by combining early-exit strategies with decentralised computing. In this context, D-Exit addresses critical challenges in latency, communication, computational efficiency, and scalability of real-time AI inference applications across distributed networks of heterogeneous devices. Moreover, D-Exit enhances the key aspect of resilience in fully distributed swarm systems that run AI-intensive inference tasks, allowing for seamless addition or removal of swarm nodes, providing a dynamic adaptation to network conditions and ensuring fair distribution of computational and energy load across the swarm nodes. Future directions of the present work include:

1. **Dynamic Load Balancing:** More complex algorithms need to be developed and incorporated in D-Exit to balance the real-time load between the heterogeneous swarm nodes.
2. **Model Consistency and Updates:** Mechanisms for online updating the DNN branches hosted in the swarm nodes and ensuring the consistency of the overall model version across distributed nodes are required.
3. **Privacy-Preserving Techniques:** The D-Exit framework can be integrated with additional privacy-preserving methods, such as blockchain-assisted techniques, differential privacy or encryption of the feedforward data.
4. **Scalability and Peer Churning:** Scalability and reliability concerns of the D-Exit framework will be investigated, focusing on energy consumption trade-offs in larger swarm sizes, as well as assessing the resilience in decentralized vs centralized schemes by conducting failure injection simulations (node dropout) [7].

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